

INFLUENCE OF FERTILIZER RATES AND ACTIVE BIOSTIMULANTS ON THE CROP ELEMENTS AND PRODUCTIVITY OF TRITICALE VARIETY "DOSTLIK-4"

¹Kushmatov B.S., ²Isakov K.T.

¹Head of the Department "Agricultural Engineering and Plant Protection" of Bakhmal Scientific Experimental Station of Lalmikor Research Institute of Agriculture, doctor of agricultural sciences

²Lalmikor Research Institute of Agriculture, Head of Laboratory

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13893574>

Abstract. *This article investigates the effects of various rates of mineral fertilizers and active biostimulants on the yield components and grain yield of the Triticale variety «Dostlik-4» in the context of soddy-podzolic soils in the mountainous region (elevation of 900-2000 meters above sea level) of agricultural fields. The findings of the study are substantiated based on the results obtained.*

Keywords: *triticale, crop elements, spike, spike length, number of grains in a spike, grain weight in one spike, 1000 grain weight, grain volume weight, yield, mineral fertilizers, biostimulant.*

At present time food security is an important area in all countries, since the growth of the world's population leads to an even greater demand for food. Therefore, the contribution of grain crops to the sustainable development of the agricultural sector is of great importance. At the same time, in countries with developed agriculture, much attention is paid to the gradual transfer of grain crops from irrigated areas to conditionally irrigated and arid areas, the creation of varieties with high resistance to drought and global variability of nature, and the development of agricultural technology for growing these varieties in the context of regions. For the effective use of irrigated areas in the context of global climate change occurring in the world today, it is important to develop agricultural technologies for growing food products and grain crops in conditionally irrigated and arid areas. In subsequent years, in order to meet the needs of the population of our republic for dairy and meat products due to internal capabilities and to reduce the weight of imports by half, as a result of fundamental reforms in the livestock industry, Triticale is grown on 12 thousand hectares of irrigated and 15 thousand hectares of dry land, and from irrigated areas an average of 65-70 c/ha is cultivated, and from arid areas 15-17 c/ha is cultivated.

It is known to everyone that growing triticale crops in arid areas gives good results in increasing the income of farms, providing the food industry with cheap and protein-rich raw materials, high-quality feed for livestock and poultry [1].

While sowing this crop at the optimal time, the grain yield is maximized, and the level of profitability of production increases [2]. Besides that, the sowing time has a significant impact on the rate of seed germination, the formation of the root system of seeds, the speed of development phases, the accumulation of sugar in nodules and leaves, resistance to winter, diseases and pests, grain yield. [3; 4; 5].

The object of the research. The meadow consisting of gray soil, triticale variety Dostlik-4, mineral fertilizers (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium), an active biostimulant (silicon aminoside).

Research methods: The primary phases of phenological observations were determined using the International Classifier for the Triticum species developed by the Russian Plant Science Institute in 1984 [5]. Biometrics measurements were conducted according to the methodology of the State Variety Testing Commission for Agricultural Crops from 1989 [6]. Field experiments were carried out following the methods established by Uzbek Scientific Research Institute of Plant Industry (UzPITI), Tashkent, in 2007 [7].

Research results. The main factors influencing the yield of triticale are the length of the spike, the number of spikelets in the spike, the number of grains in one spike and the weight of 1000 grains. The formation of the elements of the triticale yield is also affected by the timing of sowing, seeding rates and mineral fertilizer application rates [9, 10]. In the reporting year, in the control (without fertilizers) variant of the 1st experiment, the plant height was 90.3 cm, the number of productive stems was 98.2, productive bunches were 1.2, the number of grains in one spike was 18.7, the weight of grains in one spike was 1.2 g / m, the length of the spike was 9.9 cm, the weight of 1000 grains was 40.1 g / nit, the grain weight was 811.8 g / nit. The rest of the experiment P30K30 (background) before planting, (background)+N30 susp+1 plant/day, (background)+N40 susp+1 plant/day, (background)+N50 susp+1 plant/day, (background)+N30 suspension+2 grooves/day, (background)+N40 suspension+2 grooves/yes, (background)+N50 suspension+2 grooves/day, and (background)+N30 suspension+2 bushing+groove/yes, (background)+in variants 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11, mineral fertilizers and active biostimulants were used in the mode N40 susp+2 bush+pipe/yes, (background)+N50 susp+2 bush+pipe/yes, plant height - 90.3-96.7 cm, the number of productive stems is 136.2-202.0 pcs., productive bunch is 1.0-1.2 pcs., the number of grains in one spike is 18.7-29.1 pcs., the weight of grains in one spike is 1.2-1.8 g / p, the length of the spike is 9.9-11.5 cm, the weight of 1000 grains is 40.1-45.6 g / p, the bulk density of grain is 811.8-825.9 g / p per liter. (Table-1)

Table-1

The influence of mineral fertilizer rates and active biostimulants on the yield elements of triticale varieties Dostlik-4, Bakhmal-2023

№	Rate of mineral fertilizers and active biostimulants, kg/ha	Plant height, cm	Number of productive stems, pcs	Productive accumulation, pcs	The number of grains in one pcs	Grain weight in one spike, g	Spike length	Weight of 1000 bonds, g	Grain volume weight, g/liter
1	Control (without fertilizer)	90,3	136,2	1,0	18,7	1,2	9,9	40,1	811,8
2	P ₃₀ K ₃₀ (Background) before planting	92,6	155,2	1,1	21,5	1,5	10,2	40,2	813,8
3	(Background)+N ₃₀ susp +1 bush/ha, 2 l/ha	93,1	159,8	1,1	22,4	1,4	10,5	41,8	818,9
4	(Background)+N ₄₀ susp+1 bush/ha, 2 l/ha	93,1	154,5	1,1	23,6	1,4	10,5	42,0	819,6
5	(Background)+N ₅₀ susp +1 bush/ha, 2 l/ha	93,6	166,5	1,1	23,8	1,4	10,6	42,0	819,0

6	(Background) + N ₃₀ susp +2 tubes/ha, 2 l/ha	95,4	164,5	1,1	22,8	1,5	10,8	42,1	821,0
7	(Background) + N ₄₀ susp +2 tubes/ha, 2 l/ha	95,6	179,0	1,1	24,6	1,5	10,9	42,3	821,3
8	(Background) + N ₅₀ susp +2 tubes/ha, 2 l/ha	95,7	185,5	1,1	26,5	1,5	10,8	43,2	819,6
9	(Background)+N ₃₀ susp +2 bush+pipe/da, 2 l/ha	96,7	192,3	1,1	22,1	1,7	11,2	44,1	820,3
10	(Background)+N ₃₀ susp +2 bush+pipe/da, 2 l/ha	96,8	193,8	1,2	27,8	1,7	11,3	44,1	821,2
11	(Background)+N ₃₀ susp +2 bush+pipe/da, 2 l/ha	96,8	202,0	1,2	29,1	1,8	11,5	45,6	825,9

According to the research results, the yield elements of the triticale variety Dostlik-4 are the highest in the 11th variant of the experiment (Background) + suspension H50 + 2 bushes + pipe/biostimulator, plant height - 96.8 cm, number of productive stems - 202.0 pcs., 2 pcs., number of grains in one ear - 29.1, weight of grains in one ear - 1.8 g/l, ear length - 11.8 cm, weight of 1000 grains is 45.6 g/l, and the bulk density of grain is 825.9 g/l, compared to the control (without fertilizers) option 1, plant height is 6.5 cm, the number of productive stems is 65.8, the productive bunch is 0.2, the number of grains in one ear is 10.4, the weight of grains in one ear is 0.6 g, the length of the ear is 1.9 cm, the weight of 1000 grains is 5.5 g and the bulk density of grain is 14.1 g/l. The yield is one of the main indicators of agricultural crops. While studying the grain yield in the reporting year in the control (without fertilizers) variant 1 of the experiment, the grain yield was 6.1 c / ha, and the residue P30K30 (background) before planting, (background) + H30 susp + 1 bush / day, (background) + N40 suspension + 1 bush / yes, (background) + N50 suspension + 1 bush / yes, (background) + N30 suspension + 2 grooves / yes, (background) + N40 suspension + 2 grooves / yes, (background) + N50 susp + 2 mineral fertilizers and active in options 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11, where biostimulants were used, was 9.1-15.7 c / ha, respectively.

Figure 1. Grain yield of triticale variety "Dostlik-4" from mineral fertilizers and active biostimulants, Bakhmal-2023.

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that when analyzing the triticale variety Dostlik-4 for grain yield, the highest result was 15.7 c / ha in the 11th variant of the experiment (Background) + H50 susp + 2. tup + nay /, in which a biostimulant was used, and in the control (without fertilizers) in option 1, an additional grain yield of 6.1 t / ha and 7.7 t / ha was obtained compared to the control (without fertilizers).

By summarizing it can be concluded that in the mountainous region of arid regions, the application of mineral fertilizers H50P30K30 (temkh) per hectare and active biostimulants twice during the period of budding and tuber formation of the plant gives a good result in growing high-quality grain crops of the triticale variety Dostlik-4.

REFERENCES

1. Adilov H., Isakov K., Umirov N. "Breeding of triticale in dryland farming" *Agroscience* 4 (20) 2011 issue. P. 30
2. Biryukov Konstantin Nikolaevich "Justification of the timing of sowing new varieties of winter triticale on southern chernozems of the Rostov region", Abstract of dissertation 2012; P.18.
3. Sadullaevich K. B., Meylikovich K. B. The Effect of Planting Period, Seed and Mineral Fertilizers on Harvest Elements and Yield of Triticale "Sardor" Variety // *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*. 2023. T. 18. – P. 32-36.
4. Isakov K., Kushmatov B., Tukhtamishev E. "The development of scientific and technological progress in the field of education and science" // *Prospects of Development of Science and Education*. 2023. Vol. 19.– N. 23. – P. 80-82.
5. Dragavtsev V.A. Mechanism of plant integrity, phytocenosis, organism-environment system // Abstract of the report of the 3rd Congress of the All-Russian Society of Plant Physiologists. – St. Petersburg, 1993. – Vol. 3. – P. 297
6. Phenological observations according to the International Classification of SEV Triticum species of 1984.
7. *Agricultural crops*, 1989, State Variety Testing method [6].
8. *Conducting field experiments UzPITI*, Tashkent, 2007 method.
9. Pominov A. V., Initial material for selection in the Lower Volga region: author's abstract. dis. candidate of biological sciences: – Saratov, 2015. P. 29.
10. Kushmatov B. S., Kholikov B. M. A study of influence of sowing time, seed and mineral fertilizer rates on triticale "Sardor" variety productivity indicators // *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 9. – P. 643-648.